

EVALUATION OF THE ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES BY THE VARYING-SPAN METHOD

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SUMMARY: Fiber reinforced plastic composites suffer from low shear modulus. Therefore, when such materials are subjected to three- or four-point bending tests, the predicted longitudinal modulus will include the effect of shear deformation, except when the specimen has a large span to depth ratio (L/h). This characteristic was used by the authors to introduce the potential of a new methodology for the simultaneous evaluation of the longitudinal and shear moduli (E and G) of composite materials [1]. In the present work, the proposed testing method is used to evaluate the properties of graphite/epoxy and Kevlar/epoxy composites. The effect of variable strain rates which is inherent in the method is also studied, and the results are presented. The results agree very well with those obtained by the other methods thereby confirming the integrity, efficiency and the reliability of the proposed method. The reliability of the method is also investigated and confirmed by the statistical means.

KEYWORDS: composite materials, fiber reinforced plastics, testing methods, tensile modulus, through-the-thickness shear modulus, shear modulus, varying-span method.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastic composites (FRPC) can be classified as orthotropic materials with 9 independent elastic constants. Referring to Fig. 1, these constants are the elastic Moduli (E_{11} , E_{22} , E_{33}), the Poisson's ratios (ν_{12} , ν_{13} , ν_{23}), and the shear moduli (G_{12} , G_{13} , G_{23}) in orthogonal directions. To evaluate these properties several methods have been developed and used. However, only a few methods have gained popularity in practice. For instance, the standard procedure for evaluating tensile modulus and strength and the Poisson's ratio of FRPC is to subject a flat and rectangular specimen to direct tensile loading (ASTM D3039-93). One must, however, ensure that any bending due to misalignment of the specimen and/or the system itself is minimized. The specimens must be tabbed at the grip regions to ensure that they will not fail prematurely due to stress concentration. Moreover, hydraulic grips (very costly) are often required when testing moderately thick laminates.

Due to the above stringent requirements, and the simplicity and ease offered by a flexural test, ASTM flexural test method D790M-93 has gained a special popularity in industry. However, due to the shear coupling effect, the flexural modulus obtained by this method for specimens with small span to depth ratios (L/h) is not reliable. To eliminate this problem, Zweben et al. [2] suggested the use of specimens with $L/h > 60$. The flexural modulus obtained for specimens with the aspect ratios greater than 60 agrees well with the result of the tensile test [3], however the flexural strength are usually more than the tensile strength obtained by the

tensile test. The latter difference should not be construed as a shortfall of the method. Indeed, most structures are subjected to flexural loading in service. Therefore, the response of the material in flexural test is actually very close to its condition in service.

Fig.2: Definition of material principal axes for a lamina.

The most accurate results for the shear properties are believed to be obtained by applying a torsion load to a thin wall tube specimen [4]. Nevertheless, because of the difficulty involved in the preparation of the tubular specimen, other methods are usually employed in industry. The most common methods for the evaluation of shear properties are rail shear test [5] (ASTM D4255M-83), 10° off-axis [6], $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test [7] (ASTM3518-94), Iosipescu [8] (ASTM D5379-93), and the short-beam [9] (ASTM D2344-84) shear test. Among these methods, with the exception to the short-beam and the Iosipescu shear tests, non of the others can be used to evaluate the out-of-plane properties of FRPC. Moreover, the short-beam shear test can provide only an apparent through-the-thickness shear strength of a material, while the Iosipescu shear test requires a specimen with minimum thickness of 20 mm (hence, difficult to prepare). The shortfalls identified above indicate a distinct requirement for a more practical test method capable of evaluating the through-the-thickness shear modulus of FRPC. An in depth overview of the advantages and disadvantages of the above test methods was presented in Ref. 1 and 10.

In summary, common to most of the available test methods, the specimens are not subjected to a combined state of stresses that they often experience during their service. Therefore, the evaluated properties from these methods may not represent the true in service behavior of the materials. The ideal test method would have the following additional capabilities and attributes.

- 1- would use specimens extracted directly from as-received materials.
- 2- would use specimens with simple geometry.
- 3- would not require additional alteration and machining of the specimen.
- 4- would use a simple fixture, without elaborate mounting requirement.
- 5- would not require strain gages and/or other expensive instrumentation.
- 6- would produce reliable results.
- 7- would be capable of providing several properties from the same set of tests.

The proposed method in this work is believed to have most of the desired attributes of the above list. The method is based on subjecting rectangular specimens with different span to depth ratio (L/h) to three-point bending. Therefore, the proposed test method is referred to as “the Varying-Span Method” (VSM), hereafter. Both longitudinal modulus and the through-the-thickness shear modulus of the specimens along with the flexural and interlaminar shear

strengths can be obtained from the recorded data. A detailed discussion of the parameters influencing the accuracy and the efficiency of this method presented is presented in Ref. 1. Here, after a short review of the relevant theories, we will examine the influence of different strain rate (for different L/h) imposed by the proposed method on the properties of graphite/epoxy and a Kevlar/epoxy FRPC. The properties evaluated under this situation are reported and are compared with those obtained by other methods.

THEORY

In our previous work [1] two different approaches for evaluating the properties of FRCP were examined. In one of the approaches the application of the through-the-thickness inextensibility was discussed. This approach is believed to provide more accurate results in comparison to the other approach. However, it is associated with elaborated mathematics, and it has lengthier procedure. The second approach is based on the application of Timoshenko beam theory [11]. This approach, though not as accurate as the first approach, is however, more straight forward. A review of the second procedure and its theory is presented.

Consider a simply supported specimen carrying a concentrated load at mid-span that is subjected to three-point bending (Fig. 2a). Since the localized deformation under the concentrated load and also at the supports cannot be predicted by the Timoshenko beam theory, we define the net mid-span deflection as follows

$$\Delta = \Delta_A - \Delta_B \quad (1)$$

where Δ_A and Δ_B are the displacements of points A and B in the z direction, respectively. To compensate for the effect of the concentrated load and the reaction forces on the net mid-span deflection, we assume the load and the reactions are applied over a finite length (for a comprehensive discussion on this matter see Ref. 12).

In Timoshenko beam theory the total deflection is composed of the portion that results from flexure of the beam and the other portion resulting from its shear deformation. They can be calculated separately, and the net deflection at mid-span can be written as:

$$\Delta = \Delta_{flexural} + \Delta_{shear} \quad (2)$$

Referring to Fig. (2b), one can represent the components of the deflections by

$$\Delta_{flexural} = \frac{F}{48EI} (L^3 - 2\bar{b}^2 + \bar{b}^3) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_{shear} = \frac{3F}{10AG} (L - 1.5\bar{b}) \quad (4)$$

Substituting these equations into Eqn 2 gives

$$\Delta = \frac{F}{48EI} (L^3 - 2\bar{b}^2 + \bar{b}^3) + \frac{3F}{10AG} (L - 1.5\bar{b}) \quad (5)$$

where I and A are the moment of inertia and the area of the beam section, respectively. The value of \bar{b} plays an important role in the accuracy of the results, and it is more convenient to set it as a fraction of the beam depth.

$$\bar{b} = \alpha h \quad (6)$$

The value of α is not constant and depends to the geometry of the specimen and the properties of the material. The exact value of α can be obtained from the graphs presented in Ref. 1. However, pre requisite to use of the graphs is the knowledge of the material properties. If no data exists, admissible values can be obtained by the rule of mixture. Nevertheless as it was shown in Ref. 1, for practical purposes the use of an approximate value $\alpha=0.7$ can produce reliable results. When the width to depth ratio of the specimens are approximately 5, the expected errors with this assumption will be lower than 0.5% for E and lower than 4.5% for G . With some manipulations one can write Eqn 5 in the following form.

$$\frac{1}{E'} = \frac{1}{E} + \frac{1}{G} J \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where

$$E' = \frac{F}{4\Delta b} \left[\left(\frac{L}{h} \right)^3 - 2\alpha^2 \frac{L}{h} + \alpha^3 \right] \quad (8)$$

$$J = 1.2 \frac{\frac{L}{h} - 1.5\alpha}{\frac{L}{h} - 2\alpha^2 \frac{h}{L} + \alpha^3 \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2} \quad (9)$$

and b is the width of the beam. In the above, E' is the apparent modulus of elasticity that includes the shear effect. Therefore, E' is not a constant value and changes as a function of the span. E' value, however, approaches E when L/h ratio becomes reasonably large. J is always smaller than 1.2 and approaches to this value for large L/h .

Fig. 2: Equivalence of the concentrated and the reactions forces with uniformly distributed loads.

Equation 7 as outlined in Fig. 3 is the equation of a line that will be referred to as the “characteristic line” of the material hereafter. The intercept and the slope of this line represent $1/E$ and $1/G$ of the material, respectively. Therefore, for establishing the characteristic line of a material one needs to perform at least two flexural tests (Fig. 2a), on specimens with

different spans. The slope of the load-deflection curve of each test provides a F / Δ value for Eqn 8, from which one can calculate the E' value that corresponds to a specific value of $J(h/L)^2$. Since each test produces a point in the coordinate system of Fig. 3, having the results of two tests, theoretically, enables one to define the properties of the characteristic line. However, to improve the accuracy and the reliability of the results, it is necessary to do more than two tests and therefore, one needs to employ a linear regression analysis to obtain the best fitted line.

Fig. 3: The characteristic line of the material

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The proposed method was examined by conducting a series of tests on 0° unidirectional graphite/epoxy and Kevlar/epoxy specimens. The specimens of graphite/epoxy were cut from 300×300 mm hand lay-up panels composed of 24 layers of Fiberite graphite/epoxy prepreg. The panels were vacuum bagged and were cured in an autoclave with the curing cycle specified by the supplier of the prepreg. The panels were then cut into strips of approximately 12.5 mm width from which the specimens with different lengths were obtained. To eliminate the excess resin rich surface layers of the specimens and also insuring uniform and smooth thickness, the specimens were sanded with No. 400 silicon carbide powder. The thickness of the specimens for the VSM varied between 2.51 and 2.72 mm. The same procedure was followed to prepare the specimens for tensile tests. Three specimens with 25 mm width were also cut from a cross ply laminate panel at angle 45° for the ASTM $\pm 45^\circ$ shear tests. The thickness of the specimens for the tensile test was between 2.33 and 2.51 mm and for the $\pm 45^\circ$ shear test it varied between 2.41 and 2.51 m. The specimens of Kevlar/epoxy were cut from a 150 mm pultruded panel with an average thickness of 1.9 mm. The width of the specimens was about 12.5 mm. No sanding or polishing was applied.

The specimens were tested by the use of a special apparatus designed and fabricated for the VSM at Technical University of Nova Scotia (TUNS). The apparatus enabled us to accurately measure the net mid-span deflection as a function of the applied load. The loading was applied by an universal MTS testing machine.

As it was mentioned in our earlier work [1], it is not possible to maintain a constant strain rate (for different L/h) for both the longitudinal and the shear deformations, simultaneously, in the VSM. To ensure a constant strain rate for the longitudinal strain, the net mid-span deflection rate must vary according to the following equation

$$\dot{\Delta} = \dot{\epsilon}_{\max} L \left[0.2 \frac{E}{G} \frac{h}{L} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{L}{h} \right] \quad (10)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{\max}$ is the strain rate at the outermost layer of the specimen. To produce a constant shear strain rate the following relation must hold

$$\dot{\Delta} = \dot{\gamma}_{avr} L \left[0.6 + 0.5 \frac{G}{E} \left(\frac{L}{h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}_{avr}$ is the average shear strain rate of the section. It should be noted that a constant net mid-span deflection could not be maintained by our loading machine; consequently, the deflection rates from Eqns 10 and 11 were directly used to establish the speed of the actuator for each test. Eqns 10 and 11 indicate that in order to produce a constant longitudinal or shear strain rates a knowledge of the approximate value of E/G is necessary. It should be noted that the results are not very sensitive to this parameter. In fact, our analysis indicated that for $L/h \cong 30$, under a constant longitudinal strain rate, a large variation in the assumed value of E/G did not appreciably change the resulting speed of the actuator. However, for $L/h \cong 5.5$ the speed for $E/G=30$ is only 1.5 times of what is required for $E/G=10$. This difference in the speed of the actuator cannot have a considerable effect on the results of common composite materials which, in general, are not very strain rate sensitive. Furthermore, it is instructive to note that the pre-assumption of E/G value is not a difficult task. Such a value can be obtained with a reasonable accuracy from relevant literature and/or by the use of the rule of mixture. Nevertheless, several tests were conducted to establish the validity of the claims made on the effect E/G and also the influence of the strain rate as obtained by Eqns 10 and 11. The variables for all tests are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: Test variables for different sets of specimens

Designation	Material	Equation	E/G	$\dot{\epsilon}_{\max}$	$\dot{\gamma}_{avr}$
GR-1	Graphite/epoxy	10	30	0.01	var.
GR-2	Graphite/epoxy	10	30	0.01	var.
GR-3	Graphite/epoxy	10	10	0.01	var.
GR-4	Graphite/epoxy	11	30	var.	0.01
K-1	Kevlar/epoxy	10	30	0.01	var.
K-2	Kevlar/epoxy	10	30	0.01	var.
K-3	Kevlar/epoxy	10	10	0.01	var.
K-4	Kevlar/epoxy	10	10	0.01	var.
K-5	Kevlar/epoxy	11	30	var.	0.01
K-6	Kevlar/epoxy	11	30	var.	0.01

Each sets of specimens were tested with 5 different spans. At least three specimens were tested for each span. Each specimen was tested twice. In the first test, depending to the linearity limit, the specimen was loaded to about 50% to 80% of its failure load. The test was stopped before the specimen showed significant nonlinearity. In the second test, the specimen was loaded to failure. The initial slope of the load-deflection curve of each test was evaluated. This value was used to represent F / Δ in Eqn 10 and its corresponding E' was calculated. A plot of $1 / E'$ versus $J(h / L)^2$ for the results obtained from the first time loading is presented

in Fig. 4. A similar plot was obtained for the results of the second time loading, however for the sake of brevity the plot is not presented in here. The E and G value obtained from different sets of specimen are presented in Table 2 and 3. As stated earlier, an approximate value of $\alpha=0.7$ was used for all cases.

The overall distributions of the data points in Fig. 4, for both materials, present a linear trend, therefore, confirming the applicability of the proposed method for the selected materials. Furthermore, the results do not indicate an obvious dependency to the different situations tabulated in Table 1. Consequently, it can be concluded that the varying strain rate imposed by the proposed test method did not influence the results. The selected speeds of the actuator used for testing three different sets of beams having $L/h < 15$ were comparable. For $L/h \geq 30$, the required speed of the actuator to produce a constant shear strain rate for $E/G=30$ was about 3 times higher than that required for maintaining a constant longitudinal strain rate. This ratio approaches to 9 for $E/G=10$. However, since in specimens with large L/h only a very small portion of the deflection is due to the shear deformation, thus, the significance of maintaining a constant shear strain rate vanishes. On the other hand, the importance of constant longitudinal strain rate increases as L/h becomes large. It should be noted that based on the application of the proposed method, there is no apparent relation between the properties obtained for the selected materials and the various strain rates that was imposed during testing. However, it is recommended that Eqn 10 (along with an appropriate value of E/G) be used for general purposes.

Figure 4: Plot of $1/E'$ versus $J(h/L)^2$

Table 2: G_{13} and E_{11} of Graphite/epoxy (GPa)

Designation	First loading				Second loading			
	GR-1	GR-2	GR-3	GR-4	GR-1	GR-2	GR-3	GR-4
E_{11}	151.9	150.8	155.8	149.4	151.0	153.1	156.4	151.0
G_{13}	4.55	4.59	4.32	5.07	4.87	4.7	4.44	4.88

Table 3: G_{13} and E_{11} of Kevlar/Epoxy (GPa)

Group	First loading						Second loading					
	K-1	K-2	K-3	K-4	K-5	K-6	K-1	K-2	K-3	K-4	K-5	K-6
E_{11}	66.9	67.9	69.7	68.3	67.6	69.4	66.0	68.4	68.9	67.6	67.4	68.3
G_{13}	1.82	1.75	1.59	1.71	1.73	1.68	1.76	1.62	1.58	1.69	1.68	1.73

For comparison and validation of the results of the longitudinal and shear moduli obtained by the proposed method, other standard test methods were also used. The longitudinal modulus of the materials were obtained according to ASTM D3039-93 Tensile Test. The in-plane shear modulus (G_{12}) of graphite/epoxy and Kevlar/epoxy were evaluated by the ASTM $\pm 45^\circ$ and 10° off-axis shear tests, respectively. As it was mentioned earlier, there exists no simple and practical method for evaluating the out-of-plane shear modulus (G_{13}) of the materials to be used for comparing the results of the proposed method. Theoretically, if the distribution of fibers through the thickness and through the width of the laminate follows the same pattern, G_{13} and G_{12} should be equal. However, in practice the situation may not be as ideal. Moreover, in hand lay-up laminates, the layer interfaces are more susceptible to defects and therefore, a smaller out-of-plane shear modulus (G_{13}) can be expected. A summary of the results of these tests and the results obtained by the VSM are reported in Table 4. The E_{11} and the G_{13} of the VSM in this table were evaluated from the results of all the specimens. The 95% confidence bands are also reported for the results of this method. The small confidence bands confirm the reliability of the proposed method. Furthermore, as the values reported in the table show, the results obtained by the proposed method are in good agreement with those obtained by the other methods. Although the small discrepancy is quite acceptable for practical purposes, one may expect the difference to be the result of the followings:

- In tensile test, the results can be influenced by the effect of the possible bending due to specimen and/or system misalignment.
- The shear modulus obtained by the proposed method is G_{13} , however the results of the other methods are G_{12} . As explained, these values differ from one another, slightly.
- None of the shear test methods used in here is considered to be an exact method.
- 10° off-axis shear test generally gives higher value, except for specimens with very large aspect ratios [13,14].
- The fabricated fixture for the varying-span method is in its preliminary stage. Further modification and enhancements are necessary.

Table 4: Summary of the results obtained from different testing methods and 95% confidence bands (GPa)

	Graphite/epoxy			Kevlar/epoxy		
	1st loading VSM	2nd loading VSM	other methods	1st loading VSM	2nd loading VSM	other methods
E_{11}	152.4±4.5	153.1±2.9	150.8	68.3±1.3	67.8±1.3	66.6
G_{13}	4.57±0.22	4.69±0.15	—	1.72±0.06	1.68±0.07	—
G_{12}	—	—	4.87	—	—	1.90

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Among several test methods developed and used for the evaluation of elastic constants and the corresponding strength of fiber reinforced plastic composites (FRPC), three- and four-point bending tests are unique due to several inherent properties. These methods use a simple fixture to host specimens with simple rectangular geometry, and they do not require additional machining or tabbing. No strain gauge or other expensive instrumentation and/or grips are required either. However, since FRPC suffer from low shear modulus, therefore, the evaluated longitudinal modulus by these methods depends on the span to depth ratio (L/h) of the specimen used in testing. This characteristic of FRPC was used to develop a new method for

simultaneous evaluation of their longitudinal and shear moduli. The proposed method uses specimens with simple rectangular geometry and different spans, and therefore, the method is referred to as “the varying span method” (VSM). This method was used to evaluate the longitudinal and shear moduli of unidirectional 0° graphite/epoxy and 0° Kevlar/epoxy. The effect of different strain rate (for different L/h) that is inhered in this method was investigated by performing tests under three different situations, with the results presented in Table 1. No obvious dependency was observed between the obtained moduli, and the different situations. However, in general, the use of Eqn 10 which ensures a reasonable constant strain rate is recommended. The 95% confidence band of the evaluated values along with the close agreement of the results with those obtained by the other methods validate the integrity and the reliability of the proposed method.

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